

DOSS

Secure-by-Design IoT Operation with Supply Chain Control

D7.5 – Data Management Plan I.

Grant Agreement Number	101120270 — DOSS — HORIZON-CL3-2022-CS-01
Work Package No. and Title	WP7 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
Deliverable Version	1.0
Due Date	29.02.2024 (M6)
Delivery Date	28.02.2024 (M6)
Type	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Lead Beneficiary Short Name	CERTH
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101120270 - DOSS.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

Document History

Version	Date	Comments	Author
v0.1	15/10/2023	Selection of the template. Table of contents generation.	CERTH
v0.2	8/11/2023	Introduction and DOSS Project description.	CERTH
v0.3	1/12/2023	Data Summary section	CERTH
v0.4	21/12/2023	Data Security Section	CERTH
v0.5	25/01/2024	FAIR Data Section and Allocation of Resources	CERTH
v.06	13/02/2024	Ethics section	CERTH
v0.7	21/02/2024	Version ready for internal review	CERTH
v0.8	22/02/2024	Review by UMU	UMU
v0.9	23/02/2024	Review by ATOS	ATOS
v1.0	28/02/2024	Final deliverable	CERTH
V1.0	28/02/2024	Submission to EC	ATOS

The DOSS Consortium

No	Beneficiary name	Short name	Country
1	ATOS Hungary Ltd.	ATOS	Hungary
2	Centre for Research & Technology Hellas	CERTH	Greece
3	FhG FOKUS	FOKUS	Germany
4	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
5	University of Murcia	UMU	Spain
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10	Fundacion Tecnalía Research & Innovation	TECN	Spain
11	Thales Six Gts France SAS	THALES	Germany
12	Eviden Hungary Ltd.	EVIDEN	Hungary

Executive Summary

This deliverable represents the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP), capturing the initial trajectory of the project, particularly until M6. This phase marked the introduction of datasets that will be utilized throughout the project's lifecycle, the strategy for gathering project-related data, as well as for making them openly available in line with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles. This document aligns seamlessly with the Horizon Europe DMP template provided by the European Commission (EC) in the *Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020*, version 3.0, July 2016. It offers a basic understanding of the data that will be collected by the Pilots during their demonstration and evaluation activities and outlines a strengthened data security and backup strategy to ensure the utmost robustness and reliability in data management.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym	Meaning
ACM	Association for Computing Machinery
APC	Article Processing Charge
ASV	Architecture Security Validator
BO	Business Objective
CC	Creative Commons Attribution
CRA	European Cyber Resilience Act
D	Deliverable
DAST	Dynamic Application Security Testing
DCT	Digital Cybersecurity Twin
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DSP	Device Security Passport
EC	European Commission
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
EU	European Union

FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GNU	General Public License
GPL	General Public License
IAST	Interactive Application Security Testing
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IoT	Internet of Things
M	Month
MUD	Manufacturer Usage Description
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
OS	Operating System
P	Part
RPO	Recovery Point Objective
RTO	Recovery Time Objective
SAST	Static Application Security Testing
SBOM	Software Bill of Materials
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound

SOP	Secure Onboarding Platform
STC	Supply Trust Chain
TCM	Technical Committee Meeting
TSO	Technical and Scientific Objective
VEX	Vulnerability Exploitability eXchange
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope and Objective of this Deliverable

This deliverable (D7.5) aims to present the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the DOSS project as required by the project's Grant Agreement number 101120270 [1]. The document defines the data management plan and procedures for ensuring a better understanding, efficient collection, generation, processing, and storage of all datasets. Moreover, it addresses the relevant aspects of making data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable). The present deliverable was prepared based on the guidelines that are provided by the EC. We expect that sharing practices that this document sets will lead to greater visibility and overall impact of the DOSS project. Besides, the DMP will also set the standards for the collaboration between the partners, with respect to data collection and exchange.

The objective of the Data Management Plan is to define and describe the data management policy that will be applied, regarding all the data gathered, handled, and created by DOSS. The DMP will comprise information towards the direction of assisting Partners with the DOSS project to handle the research data, which means collect, process, generate, share, present, document, access, store, cooperate with other partners and also avoid replications. Lastly, the DMP smooths the communication between researchers, data managers, research funders, project partners, and academic publishers. The DMP sets the principles which rule the data lifecycle: generating, processing, analysing, handling, accessing, and re-using.

DOSS is currently at a very early stage, and it is expected that some processes may change. In particular, the purpose of the present document is to define a formal process for data collection, storage, and exchange, which will be adopted throughout the lifetime of the project. Thus, as also stated by the EC, this deliverable is a living document that we will be updated when necessary throughout the project lifetime. Any information on processes and data types will be carefully monitored and documented in the final version of this deliverable (D7.6), which is due in M30.

1.2 Deliverable Structure

In terms of structure, the content flows through six main sections, each dedicated to specific aspects of the project in line with the Horizon EU DMP template¹. Below, we provide a concise overview of each section:

- **Section 2** provides a brief description of the DOSS project.
- **Section 3** provides a detailed summary of the data that are expected to be generated, collected, and stored during the DOSS project.
- **Section 4** provides a detailed overview of how to make data easily findable, emphasizing the importance of metadata. This section presents the open access approach policy, covering aspects like Research data, the DOSS Website, DOSS OpenAIRE, DOSS Zenodo Repository, and DOSS GitHub.
- **Section 5** focuses on the resources allocated to ensure data adheres to the FAIR principles.
- **Section 6** outlines the DOSS data security policy and includes information on backup and restore strategies, reinforcing the project's commitment to data protection.
- **Section 7** introduces matters associated with ethics related to the Pilots, ensuring the project's activities remain ethically sound.

¹https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx

devices are free from vulnerabilities, weaknesses, and/or malware. The Component Tester may also verify and update the content of the DSP by providing additional security-related information for the tested components (e.g., identified vulnerabilities, etc.). The Component Tester will be defined and implemented as part of WP3.

- The *Digital Cybersecurity Twin (DCT)*: A flexibly configurable digital twin able to simulate diverse and complex IoT architectures, in order to identify and mitigate potential threats and security weaknesses already from their design (i.e., pre-deployment) phase. High-level models will be extracted from the low-level descriptions (e.g., Infrastructure-as-Code descriptions) of the IoT systems, which will be used for attack scenario identification and test case generation, as well as for impact analysis of the identified attacks. The DCT will employ AI for (i) modeling complex attack scenarios and transforming them into test cases, (ii) discovering attack surfaces, and (iii) elaborating the necessary protective countermeasures. Based on the impact analysis, the most impactful attacks will be identified and mapped to specific attack techniques, and the attacks will be tested on the digital twin to gain accurate information about their feasibility in the real world. Reports about the feasibility, impact, and severity of the attacks that were identified and tested on the DCT will be generated. The DCT provides input necessary for the Architecture Security Validator (ASV). The DCT will be defined and elaborated as part of WP4.
- The *Architecture Security Validator (ASV)*: A configurable platform responsible for assessing the compliance of modeled complex IoT architectures, as produced/prepared by the Digital Cybersecurity Twin (DCT), against relevant selected security standards, compliance requirements, and/or KPIs. The platform may be configured to which standards/regulations to consider and will provide continuous assessment of the level of compliance, highlighting failures and shortcomings. The results will also be expressed using a range of indicators. The ASV will encompass a methodology for transforming standards and regulations into formal requirements, as well as an approach for checking the compliance of a given modeled IoT architecture to these requirements in a highly automated way, providing relevant quantitative indicators. The ASV will be defined and implemented as part of WP5.
- *Secure Onboarding Platform (SOP)*: A methodology along with the appropriate tooling for the secure onboarding of devices based on the security information described in their DSPs (e.g., certificates, configuration, existing vulnerabilities, etc.). This platform will also take care of the device updates. In particular, the platform will use information securely stored in and captured from the DSP to identify and configure devices in a secure way before providing access to the designated network, as well as to ensure their secure updates. This guarantees that only tested and validated devices are attached to the networks and integrated into the broader IoT system. The platform will support the automated and secure onboarding even of a large number of IoT devices. The Secure Onboarding Platform will be defined and implemented as part of WP3.

All these elements together contribute to the definition of the secure-by-design methodology of the DOSS project towards its envisaged Supply Trust Chain (STC) concept, which ensures the security of complex IoT architectures throughout the whole lifecycle, from design to operation and decommission.

The procedures and technology will be validated in a real-world setting through three use cases stemming from three diverse IoT domains, namely automotive, energy, and smart home domains. Both quantitative and qualitative analysis will be employed in order to verify and validate the effectiveness and practicality of the proposed solutions.

This new secure-by-design approach for complex IoT operations will be an early implementation of the concept and requirements of the forthcoming European Cyber Resilience Act (CRA)² and will

²<https://www.european-cyber-resilience-act.com/>

provide an operational reference model. Based on our learnings and experiences we will make policy recommendations to make EU cybersecurity policy more effective and practical and will also contribute to IoT security related standardization.

3 DOSS Data Summary

3.1 Purpose of Data Collection and Relation to DOSS Objectives

The primary purpose of data collection within the DOSS project is to ensure the development, validation, demonstration, and operation of highly secure and resilient IoT architectures through the proposition and establishment of a STC that covers all the phases of IoT lifecycle, from design, and implementation, to operation and decommissioning, as outlined in the project objectives. The data collected will serve as a crucial resource for achieving the technical, scientific, and business objectives of the project. This is how the data collection relates to the general and various technical and business objectives of the DOSS project [1]:

General Objectives:

The DOSS project is guided by four strategic goals, as outlined in the GA document, which aim at enhancing the security and resilience of complex IoT architectures, by providing a robust digital infrastructure for securing the IoT supply chain, throughout the overall product lifecycle. In particular, the DOSS project should: (i) improve the security of IoT through the enhanced protection of its supply chain, also including the secure distribution, onboarding, and updates of system components; (ii) specify the secure-by-design operation methodology and implement the related system based on the integrated process of testing, modelling, validation, and pre-certification; (iii) validate the new tools, interactions, and workflows on three distinct IoT domains: automotive, energy, and smart home; and (iv) make policy recommendations and participate in the standardization-related activities. To accomplish these four strategic goals, the DOSS project defines 8 SMART objectives: 6 technical and scientific objectives (TSO) and 2 business objectives (BO).

Technical and Scientific Objectives (TSOs):

- **TSO 1:** The collected data will support the definition, development, and validation of the "Supply Trust Chain" concept, which is the core element of the DOSS project for ensuring end-to-end security in the IoT supply chain.
- **TSO 2:** The collected data will aid in the definition and validation of the "Device Security Passport" (DSP), which will act as a comprehensive security descriptor for IoT components, containing critical security information, such as certificates (if any), list of utilized third-party and open-source software and hardware components, vulnerability disclosure reports, and manufacturer usage description (MUD) files.
- **TSO 3:** The collected data will enable the design, implementation, and validation of the "Component Tester", which integrates security testing and validation methodologies, procedures, and tools for ensuring the security and reliability of all IoT components.
- **TSO 4:** The collected data will drive the design and implementation of operation security tools, namely the Digital Cybersecurity Twin (DCT) and the Architecture Security Validator (ASV), for ensuring (i) the proper simulation of complex IoT systems and the identification of potential threats and weaknesses already in the design phase (prior to the actual deployment and operation of the IoT system), and (ii) the compliance of the IoT system to standards, requirements, and important KPIs.
- **TSO 5:** The collected data will be essential for the implementation of a secure automated onboarding platform for system components and updates, informed by the DSP.
- **TSO 6:** The data collected from the three demonstrations will validate the proposed methods, solutions, and technologies in heterogeneous IoT service environments, providing measurable outcomes against a set of critical KPIs, confirming the efficacy of the proposed novelties in diverse IoT service scenarios.

Business Objectives (BOs):

- **BO 1:** Data related to the effectiveness and impact of the DOSS solutions will be crucial for making recommendations and contributing to the standardization activities of cybersecurity of IoT supply

chains, and potentially to the development of new standards. The activities will focus mainly on the STC and DSP concepts, attempting to reach a standard-ready maturity level.

- **BO 2:** Data collected in the DOSS project, particularly the research results and the experiences gained through the demonstrations, will serve as the foundation for making policy recommendations, providing actionable information to EU policymakers, ENISA, and regulatory authorities.

The data collected will be meticulously analysed to derive insights, validate the proposed solutions, and ensure that the DOSS project is on track to meet its objectives. The data will also be used for reporting progress, making informed decisions, and optimizing the strategies employed in the project to ensure the successful realization of the DOSS vision of enhancing IoT supply chain security. In line with DOSS objectives, data collection concerns the following groups of data:

- **System data**, that is generated and exchanged between different communication nodes of the overall system architecture, according to the foreseen use cases;
- **Integration data**, that is generated during the integration activities of the project;
- **Evaluation data**, that is additional data that needs to be collected, on top of the system data, during technical validation activities through simulation of attack scenarios, and later with users in a real-life (or close to real-life) operational environment during the project;
- **Research data**, that is gathered, or generated during the research-related activities of the DOSS project, and particularly during theoretical, analytical, or experimental investigations. This may involve datasets necessary for training and evaluating machine learning algorithms, experimental results, survey responses, and any other data that may be essential for validating research hypotheses, models, or theories;
- **Other subjective data** collected during user exploitation surveys and workshops;
- **Dissemination data** that provides evidence of dissemination activities during the DOSS project. Dissemination datasets generated during the project include relevant information for all publications including research datasets, participation in events, and online presence.

In the rest of this section, the templates that will be utilized for formally documenting the data that will be gathered, collected, generated, and or/reused during the DOSS project are presented. It should be noted that these are the main groups of data that have been identified at the current phase of the project (M6). Throughout the project's lifetime, new data categories may be identified, and, thus, new data groups may be defined, which will be documented in future updated versions of the DMP.

3.2 Template for the specification of the datasets

This subsection presents the template (see Table 1) that will be used for documenting the datasets that will be generated or collected in the DOSS project, which has been identified at this phase of the project. As the type and size of the datasets can change throughout the lifetime of the project the template may need to be modified. The illustrations of the individual datasets, including their reference, file format, standards, methodologies and metadata and repository to be employed will be presented in the next version of the DMP.

Table 1 Dataset Description Template

Dataset Description Template	
Dataset Reference	<p>"DOSS_DataType_ShortName_Date_Partner_VersionXY.ext"</p> <p>Each dataset will have a specific reference, where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ "DOSS_" is common prefix for all datasets; ▪ "DataType" is the type of the dataset (e.g. C for code, P for publication, Q for data collected via questionnaire, D for deliverable, etc.); ▪ "ShortName" is the name of the dataset; ▪ "Date" is the date of creation or submission in the form dd/mm/yyyy;

Dataset Description Template	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ "Partner" is the short name of the Partner who is responsible for the dataset. ▪ "Version" is the version number in the form: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ "X" is the version ▪ "Y" is the sub-version ▪ "ext" is the file extension according to the format used ▪ "_" underscore is used as a separator
Dataset Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Explanation of the data provenance, origin, and usefulness ▪ Explicit reference to existing data that could be reused
Standards and Metadata	The metadata attributes list and the associated standards or methodologies.
File Format	All the formats that define data
Data Origin	Data origin specification
Data Size	Expected size of the dataset
Data Sharing	<p>Explanation of the sharing policies related to the dataset between the next options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open: Open for public disposal. • Embargo: It will become public when the embargo period applied by the publisher is over. In case it is categorized as embargo, the end date of the embargo period must be written in dd/mm/yyyy format. • Restricted: Only for project internal use. <p>Each dataset must have its distribution license:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide information about personal data and mention if the data is anonymized or not. • Tell if the dataset entails personal data and how this issue is considered.
Archiving and Preservation	The preservation guarantee and the data storage during and after the project (for example: databases, institutional repositories, public repositories, etc.)
Reused existing data	Y/N. If Yes, state the reused data and how/from where they were retrieved.
Data Utility	Outline to whom the dataset could be useful – potential secondary users.

All metadata will be recorded thoroughly in **the premises of the responsible partner** before uploading or sharing to be certain to which specific data files they refer and to report all parts, files and acronyms. All records will be fixed into text files and archived with the corresponding dataset.

4 FAIR Data

DOSS Consortium has decided to follow an open-access approach respecting the EC guidelines to secure the maximum impact. DOSS project will be part of the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) [2]. Thus, the data that will be created during and after the project and will be embraced in ORDP should be 'FAIR' which means *findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable* [3]. The FAIR rules were introduced to enhance the applications of data management and data-curation, and FAIR focuses on the determination of the rules so that they then can be applied to a wide range of data management applications, whether it is data collection or data management of larger scientific projects. With the support of the FAIR rules by HEU and their application in the guidelines for HEU, the FAIR principles serve as a template for lifecycle data management and guarantee that the most crucial parts of the lifecycle are covered [4].

4.1 Making Data Findable, Including Provisions for Meta-data

In the realm of research, the accessibility, clarity, and traceability of data play pivotal roles. Ensuring that data is easily discoverable and identifiable not only enhances the transparency of our research but also fosters collaboration and knowledge dissemination. This section delves into the meticulous measures will adopt to uphold these principles, from naming conventions to metadata creation, ensuring our datasets are both robust and user-friendly.

Discoverability and Identification: All open access datasets that will be produced and/or used in the project will be uploaded to Zenodo³, a widely recognized open-access repository. Zenodo plays a crucial role in enhancing the discoverability of our datasets by providing them with comprehensive metadata.

One of the standout features of Zenodo is its automatic generation of Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for each uploaded dataset. A DOI is a persistent and unique identifier that ensures the dataset remains easily locatable and citable over time, irrespective of any changes to the dataset's storage location or web address. This feature is invaluable as it provides a stable link to the dataset, facilitating academic citations and ensuring that the dataset can always be traced back to its source.

By utilizing Zenodo's DOI generation capability, we ensure that our datasets are not only easily discoverable but also maintain their integrity and accessibility in the long run. This approach aligns with our commitment to making our research outputs transparent, traceable, and readily available to the broader scientific community and stakeholders.

Naming Conventions: Datasets within the project adhere to a consistent naming convention, which is structured as described in Table 1. The naming convention includes the project acronym, the type of the data, a short name that accurately describes the content of the dataset, the date of its creation or submission, the partner that is responsible for the dataset, and its version number. This convention ensures clarity and easy identification of datasets.

Search Keywords: To increase findability and optimize the potential for re-use, each dataset will be tagged with relevant search keywords. These keywords will be derived from the dataset's content, its purpose, and its context within the project, ensuring that potential users can easily locate the data they require. Zenodo allows performing simple and advanced search queries on Zenodo using the keywords.

Versioning: All datasets will undergo version control. Each time a dataset is updated, or modified, its version number will be incremented accordingly in order to reflect the performed update. This ensures that users can easily identify the most recent version of a dataset and trace its evolution over time.

Metadata Creation: We will adopt a specialized metadata schema tailored to the specific requirements of our research datasets. This schema will integrate critical attributes, including the dataset's title, description, timestamp of creation, authorship credentials, versioning lineage, and relevant keyword tags. By adopting this structured approach, we aim to ensure that the metadata provides a

³ <https://zenodo.org/>

comprehensive, technical overview, elucidating the dataset's intrinsic content, contextual framework, and its pertinence within the research domain.

4.2 Making Data Accessible

DOSS will guarantee open access to: (i) all peer-reviewed scientific research articles and (ii) research data (data underlying publications, curated and/or raw data). Figure 2 presents the open-access approach to scientific publication and research data in the wider context of dissemination and exploitation, as proposed in [5]. In DOSS project, we will follow the approach illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Open-access approach to scientific publications and research data [5]

4.2.1 Peer-reviewed scientific research articles

Peer-reviewed scientific publications should be accessible online for free to any user. According to [6] and [7], open access to scientific publications should include the following rights: *read, download, print, copy, distribute, search, link, crawl* and *mine*. EC proposes two key routes to open access: *self-archiving* ('green' open access) and *open-access publishing* ('gold' open access).

If an author decides to follow the **green open access** model, he must deposit the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in an online repository (before, at the same time, or after publication). However, some publishers may impose an embargo period, during which open access is prohibited.

In **gold open access** model, a scientific article is immediately published in open-access mode. The costs for gold open-access publishing (i.e., Article Processing Charges (APCs)) are usually paid by researcher's university or research institute. Following the new policy of HEU, only fees for publications that are fully open-access can be fully reimbursed. Hybrid venues (e.g., journals that support both subscription and open-access publications) are excluded.

When it comes to the publications, publishers such as IEEE, ACM, and Elsevier, lay out various options for Open Access. Both "green" and "gold" publishing concepts can be employed by the DOSS project. As it has been brought up in the IEEE guidelines for publishing papers online, the project is licenced to upload the camera-ready version of the papers/publications, to the project website without copyright notices. The guidelines for publishing IEEE, ACM, Elsevier, and Springer papers online are presented in the following links:

- http://www.ieee.org/publications_standards/publications/rights/paperversionpolicy.html
- http://www.ieee.org/documents/author_version_faq.pdf
- <http://authors.acm.org/main.html>
- <https://www.elsevier.com/about/open-science/open-access>
- <http://www.springer.com/gp/open-access/authors-rights/self-archiving-policy/2124>

The open access to publications mandate comprises three steps:

- **Step 1:** Depositing publications in repositories (online archives)
- **Step 2:** Selecting the open-access route (green or gold open access)
- **Step 3:** Providing open access to publications

Step 1: Depositing publications in repositories (online archives). All Partners must deposit an electronic copy of the publication in a suitable repository. All publications must be in a machine-readable form (i.e., in a format that is readable and understandable by computer). It is important to note that depositing is mandatory, regardless of open-access mode selected. It must be done as soon as possible, and before the publication. The project partner must deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the corresponding scientific publications ('underlying data'). It is important to note that researchers must make their publications available in (i) institutional repositories or (ii) centralized ones such as [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/) or [arXiv](https://arxiv.org/). Venues such as Research Gate⁴ or Academia.edu⁵ that require users to register to access content do not count as repositories. The posting of publications on a personal, institutional or project-specific webpage or the deposit in a public accessible Dropbox account is not sufficient to satisfy the requirements either.

Step 2: Selecting the open-access route. DOSS partners should decide between the 'green' and 'gold' open access, which are equally valid.

Step 3: Providing open access to deposited publications. DOSS partners are obliged to provide open access to scientific publications via a selected repository (i.e., institutional, Zenodo, etc.). Open access should be provided as soon as possible and no later than six months after the official publication date. If the publication is published in gold open access, the access should be provided immediately upon publication⁶.

4.2.2 Research Data

Open access to research data refers to the right to access and reuse digital data under the terms and conditions set out in the DOSS Grant Agreement. According to [5], research data refers to information (i.e., facts or numbers) collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. Papers and research data made accessible to third parties will not include any personal details.

We will record the following meta-data for all scientific papers and datasets:

- The terms: "European Union (EU)", "Horizon Europe"
- Name of the action (Research and Innovation Action)
- Acronym and grant number (DOSS, 101120270)
- Publication date
- Length of embargo period if applicable
- Persistent identifier.

When referencing Open access data, DOSS will comprise at a minimum one of the following declarations expressing EU support (with relevant information included in the repository metadata):

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101120270 – DOSS.”

⁴ <https://www.researchgate.net/>

⁵ <https://www.academia.edu/>

⁶ It should be noted that, following the new policy of HEU, only fees for venues that are fully open access can be fully reimbursed. Hybrid venues (e.g., journals that support both subscription- and open-access publications) are excluded.

The DOSS consortium will aim to make the majority of the gathered datasets open access. When this is not applicable, the data sharing chapter of that specific dataset will report why access has been restricted. The specific repositories where DOSS datasets will be held during and after the project, will be recorded in the "Archiving and Preservation" field of Table 1. In case where the project partners keep institutional repositories, these will be reported in the next DMP update. The project research papers, and in some cases research data, will be placed on the institutional repository determined by the original creator of the paper and of the data that is examined.

The dissemination of the project's data will respect the rules defined in WP7 Dissemination, communication and exploitation of results. Public deliverables (see Table 2) and any data linked or referred to them will be shared using the following ways:

- Using the DOSS website (<https://DOSS.eu/>)
- Submitting information for publication (in scientific conferences and journals, etc.)
- Making information available through the organization of conferences and workshops
- Data archives, libraries, and repositories.

Table 2 Public Deliverables of DOSS

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name
D1.3	Periodic technical and financial reports - P2
D2.1	IoT supply chain security requirements
D2.2	Integrated IoT supply chain concept
D2.3	Specification of DSP
D2.4	Prototype of STC
D3.1	Unified component testing methodology
D3.2	Component Tester
D3.3	Onboarding platform
D4.3	Digital Cybersecurity Twin
D5.2	Architecture security validator platform
D6.1	Integrated IoT supply chain architecture
D6.2	Demonstration report
D7.1	Website
D7.5	Data Management Plan I.
D7.6	Data Management Plan - P2

In the following subsections, we will give a brief description of the repositories/libraries that the project will employ for all deliverables and documents that will be generated later which will be publicly accessible.

4.2.3 DOSS Website

The project's website (<https://dossproject.eu/>), and particularly the Resources section, will be used to upload papers online.

Figure 3 DOSS Website

4.2.4 DOSS OpenAIRE

The Official OpenAIRE⁷ repository for the DOSS project⁸ is depicted in Figure 4. OpenAIRE is a European project supporting Open Science. On one hand, OpenAIRE is a system of committed Open Science specialists assisting and supplying training on Open Science. On the other hand, OpenAIRE is a technical framework collecting research output from connected data suppliers. OpenAIRE focuses on establishing an open and viable academic communication framework in charge of the overall management, analysis, manipulation, provision, monitoring and cross-linking of all research results. Some of the utilities that are provided are the following:

- Integrated scientific information: publication links, project information, datasets, per funder/project/content provider presenting them in one place
- Monitor and reporting on OS research outcomes for funders
- Training sessions and support on all subjects related to OS and OS policy
- Discovery of OS output per project, funder, data provider
- Exchange of metadata and content amongst data providers
- A general-purpose repository called Zenodo
- An Open Science helpdesk

⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

⁸ https://explore.openaire.eu/search/project?projectId=corda_he::6a414653f1577bb4de81fad7aec3c1ea

OpenAIRE EXPLORE

Search Deposit Link Data sources Funders

Link to Share Deposit Embed Download

DOSS
SECURE BY DESIGN IOT OPERATION WITH SUPPLY CHAIN CONTROL
Open Access Mandate for Publications and Research data - [EPrints](#) - 01 Sep 2023 (Started) - 31 Aug 2026 (Ending) - On going

Funder: European Commission Project code: 101120270 Call for proposal: HORIZON CL3 2022-CS 01
Funded under: HE | HORIZON-RIA Overall Budget: 4,996,940 EUR Funder Contribution: 4,996,940 EUR
Detailed Project Information (CORDIS) [→](#)

Summary DMPs

Description
DOSS elaborates a secure by design methodology and implements related technology for complex IoT architectures, based on supply chain monitoring, component testing and architecture modelling. The project establishes a "Supply Trust Chain" with integrating key stages of the IoT supply chain into a digital communication loop to facilitate security related information exchange. The technology includes security verification of all hardware and software components of the modelled architecture. A new "Device Security Passport" will be defined for 3rd party hardware and its components. 3rd party software, open source applications, as well as in house developments will be tested and assessed. The centrepiece of the proposed solution is a flexibly configurable Digital Cybersecurity Twin, able to simulate diverse IoT architectures. It will employ AI for modelling complex attack scenarios, discovering attack surfaces, and elaborating the necessary protective measures. The digital twin will provide input for a configurable, automated Architecture Security Validator module which will assess and provide pre-certification for the modelled IoT architecture in respect of relevant, selectable security standards and KPIs. To also ensure adequate coverage for the back end of the supply chain the operation of the architecture will also be protected by secure device onboarding, diverse security and monitoring technologies and a feedback loop to the digital twin and actors of the supply chain, smart...

Partners
PHG, ITS PAN, BUTE, RED-ALERT LABS, SAFEPAY, University of Murcia, PAN, Thales France, ATOS HUNGARY LTD, EVGEN HUNGARY LTD, TECNALIA, CERTH, ASVIN OMSB

[View more >](#)

Figure 4 OpenAIRE repository for DOSS project

4.2.5 DOSS Zenodo Repository

The central repository Zenodo, which is recommended for the Horizon EU projects will be employed for uploading deliverables and papers as it is connected to the OpenAIRE platform. Zenodo is an all-purpose open scientific repository. It was generated by OpenAIRE and CERN to provide a place for scientists to place publications, datasets and other research artifacts such as code, posters, presentations. Zenodo does not impose any requirements on format, size, access restrictions or licence and is not limited to one founder, or one nation. It is free to use for all research outputs from across all areas. Figure 5 shows the Zenodo repository for the DOSS project.

Horizon Europe - DOSS Project - Secure-by-Design IoT Operation with Supply Chain Control
<https://dossproject.eu/> Project [New upload](#)

Records Requests Members Settings

2 results found Sort by Newest

Versions
 View all versions

Access status
 Open 2

Resource types
 Publication 2

Subjects
 Intrusion Detection 2

December 1, 2023 (v1) Conference paper [Open](#)
Decentralized Online Federated G-Network Learning for Lightweight Intrusion Detection
Nakip, Mert, Gül, Baran Can, Gelenbe, Erol
Cyberattacks are increasingly threatening networked systems, often with the emergence of new types of unknown (zero-day) attacks and the rise of vulnerable devices. Such attacks can also target multiple components of a Supply Chain, which can be protected via Machine Learning (ML)-based Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs). However, the need to le...
Uploaded on December 1, 2023

November 1, 2023 (v1) Conference paper [Open](#)
Protecting IoT Servers Against Flood Attacks with the Quasi Deterministic Transmission Policy
Gelenbe, Erol, Nasereddin, Mohammed
Servers at Supply Chains that receive packets from IoT devices should meet the QoS needs of incoming packets, and protect the system from Cyberattacks. UDP Floods are often part of Cyberattacks that overwhelm Supply Chains and the IoT through congestion that paralyzes their operation and limits their ability for timely Attack Detection. Thus th...
Uploaded on November 18, 2023

Figure 5 Zenodo repository for DOSS

4.2.6 DOSS GitHub

Depending on the software that will be produced, safe repositories are instantiated. In order to provide access to the software created by the DOSS project, the GitHub repository will be used. Using GitHub can provide long term public access. Yet, due to security restrictions, maintaining repositories locally and then publishing on GitHub may be more suitable. Consequently, a GitHub repository has been created for the DOSS project and it will be used to host the open access software generated by the project. The link to GitHub account, depicted in Figure 6, is <https://github.com/doss-eu>.

Figure 6 DOSS Github page

4.3 Making Data Interoperable

In the DOSS project, interoperability is achieved through the use of a data bus, which facilitates the sharing of threat reports generated by various components with third-party applications. This data bus, will be implemented using Apache Kafka, and will act as a distributed streaming platform, enabling real-time data pipelines and applications to efficiently process, store, and analyze vast amounts of data. By using Kafka, we ensure that critical data can be exchanged and re-used across different researchers, institutions, organizations, and countries.

5 Allocation of Resources

Costs Incurred for Making Data FAIR. Throughout the duration of the project, part of the budget will be dedicated to ensuring that our data is in strict alignment with the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles. This allocation is not only pivotal in maintaining the integrity and accessibility of our data but also covers the associated costs for publishing our scientific findings in reputable Open Access journals, ensuring that our research outcomes are readily available to the broader scientific community and stakeholders. This commitment underscores our dedication to transparency and the dissemination of knowledge.

Coverage of Costs: The expenses associated with making our data FAIR will be covered by our Horizon EU grant, in line with the Grant Agreement conditions. We will ensure that a dedicated portion of our grant is specifically reserved for these data management activities, reinforcing our commitment to FAIR data principles.

Long-Term Preservation Resources: The importance of long-term data preservation is a key consideration in our project. To this end, our research datasets, which will be an integral part of our project's legacy, will be securely archived on Zenodo. This ensures their long-term preservation and accessibility, aligning with our commitment to open science and knowledge dissemination.

6 Data Security

In the DOSS Consortium, the safeguarding of data is of paramount importance. Recognizing the diverse nature of our operations and the varying technical requirements of our pilots, we are implementing stringent data security measures tailored to the specific needs of each initiative.

It is imperative to note that none of our pilots involves the collection of personal data, further simplifying our data protection requirements and ensuring that privacy risks are inherently minimized. However, the absence of personal data does not diminish our commitment to data security. Only authenticated personnel will have access to pilot-specific data gathered to secure the collected data and prevent unauthorised access to the DOSS data repositories.

6.1 Backup and Restore Strategies

Local data repositories and data sets

The DOSS Consortium recognizes the criticality of robust backup and restore mechanisms, particularly for datasets not housed in public repositories. Given the diverse nature of our operations and the varying technical requirements of our pilot programs and technical providers, a one-size-fits-all backup strategy is not deemed appropriate. Instead, we adopt a tailored approach, where the backup strategy is aligned with the specific operational needs, available resources, data criticality, and predefined recovery time objectives (RTO) and recovery point objectives (RPO) of each partner organization.

However, to ensure a baseline level of data protection across the consortium, we have mandated a minimum requirement for all partners. Each partner is required to implement a full backup strategy. This entails creating a comprehensive copy of their entire dataset at regular intervals. The stipulated frequency for these backups is weekly. This approach ensures that, in the event of data loss or corruption, a recent version of the data can be restored, minimizing potential disruptions and data discrepancies. Besides, the OpenAIRE website, Zenodo, and GitHub guarantee the data's maintenance due to the archiving and backup capabilities.

DOSS Integration environment

Ensuring the data security of the DOSS project infrastructure is paramount to the integrity and reliability of the system. The following measures and strategies will be implemented to safeguard the data and maintain the robustness of the DOSS project:

Infrastructure Deployment: The DOSS project infrastructure will be deployed on virtual machines (VMs) hosted by dedicated services like Hedzner, etc. Each technical provider is free to use the hosting service that is more convenient to them, or even opt to host their solutions locally (on servers located in their premises), provided that all the agreed requirements for data security, privacy, backup and restore strategies are properly followed.

Daily Backups: To ensure data integrity and availability, the VMs will undergo daily backups. This means that every 24 hours, a snapshot of the entire system's state will be captured and stored. These backups are retained for a period of 7 days, allowing us to revert to any system state within the past week if necessary.

Stable Version Maintenance: In addition to the daily backups, a stable version of each VM of the broader system will be maintained. In that way, we will ensure that a fully functional and tested version of the system is always up and running. In the event of a significant system failure or emergency, this stable version can be used to quickly rebuild the platform, ensuring minimal downtime and service disruption.

Firewall and Traffic Management: To bolster our system's security against external threats, we will establish a stringent firewall setup. This firewall is configured to permit traffic exclusively from members of the DOSS consortium. In particular, users will have to authenticate themselves prior to accessing any project assets, whereas specific roles will be assigned to the users to further enhance the security. By restricting access in this manner, we minimize the risk of unauthorized access, potential breaches, and malicious activities. To this end, all the service modules of the project will have identity and access control.

In conclusion, the backup and security strategy for the DOSS integration environment is designed to be both proactive, by preventing potential issues, and reactive, by having measures in place to quickly address and rectify any problems that may arise.

6.2 Sharing Data within the Consortium

For files that are used throughout the internal administration, the repository Redmine has been chosen. In Redmine, as Figure 7 demonstrates, discrete folders have been instantiated for Background documents, Deliverables, Dissemination material, Meetings, Publications, TCMs, Templates and Work packages. Furthermore, by using this repository, the documents will be accessible for a long period even after the completion of the project. Redmine is an open-source flexible project management web application. It is released under the terms of the GNU General Public License v2 (GPL).

The screenshot shows the Redmine interface for the DOSS repository. The top navigation bar includes 'Home', 'My page', 'Projects', and 'Help'. Below this is a blue header with the text 'DOSS'. A secondary navigation bar contains tabs for 'Overview', 'Activity', 'Issues', 'Spent time', 'Gantt', 'Calendar', 'News', 'DMS', 'Documents', 'Wiki', and 'Files'. The 'Documents' section is active, displaying a filter for 'Title' with a dropdown set to 'contains' and an empty search box. Below the filter are 'Apply' and 'Clear' buttons. The main content is a table with the following data:

#	Title	Size	Date
309	Background documents		09/01/2023 01:07 AM
362	Deliverables		01/11/2024 01:39 PM
346	Dissemination material		11/18/2023 02:22 PM
314	Meetings		09/13/2023 10:53 PM
348	Publications		11/18/2023 02:23 PM
334	TCMs		10/03/2023 07:57 PM
347	Templates		11/18/2023 02:22 PM
316	Workpackages		09/22/2023 02:57 PM
1069	Supply Trust Chain w changes	84.3 KB	12/01/2023 04:02 PM

Figure 7 Redmine DOSS repository

7 Ethics

DOSS will voluntarily participate in the Open Research Data Pilot. In this context, a detailed data management plan (this deliverable), describes the procedures for ensuring that the data management process complies with all relevant national and EU Legislation. DOSS project does not introduce any critical ethical issues or problems; nevertheless, several considerations typical to ICT applications and on-site pilot trials shall be considered. The Consortium is fully aware of these and has the necessary experience to address them seamlessly. Ethical requirements and methodology are discussed and described in D8.1 – OEI-Requirements No.1. In particular, in D8.1, we have:

- Identified a set of mandatory ethical requirements
- Proposed overall ethical management methodology
- Discussed and indicated important EU and national legislation rules and procedures

Through an in-depth analysis and a standardized approach using an ethics questionnaire, pilot operators determined that no specific ethical measures are needed for any of the pilot operations. The ethics and policy for the collection of private data for each pilot can be summarized as follows:

- **Smart Home Pilot:** The Smart Home pilot is not planned to collect and process any personal and sensitive data. The pilot use case will focus solely on collecting data from energy smart meters and environmental sensors. No other personal or sensitive data will be collected during the pilot operations, ensuring data privacy and security.
- **Prosumer Cell Pilot:** The Prosumer Cell pilot will not expose any personal data of anyone, not even the owner of the cell. In this particular installation the energy generated is used by an industrial facility where much of the power is used by an always active data centre. Looking at total power usage figures, it is impossible to tell anything about the individual people working at the site.
- **Connected Car Pilot:** As the Connected Car pilot will be performed in an artificial environment, without real, private person users, it can be safely concluded that the data managed by the Connected Car pilot demonstrator platform is not suitable to identify personal or sensitive data. Consequently, it can be established that the Connected Car pilot has no ethics relevance from a personal data management perspective, which issue was raised in the Ethics Summary Report.

Finally, it should be noted that given the utilization of AI in various aspects of the pilot demonstrations, the AI-related ethical concerns have to be taken into account. This information is reported in the “D8.1 – OEI – Ethics requirements v1.0” deliverable, which provides the ethics report of the DOSS project.

8 Conclusions

This deliverable offers the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) of the DOSS project, describing the main strategy that will be followed within the project with respect to the collection, processing, storage, and sharing of the data that will be generated or reused throughout its lifetime. It also reports our planned strategy for handling open access information and abiding by the FAIR principles, whereas it also provides information about the steps that we will take for ensuring data security along with a discussion about potential ethical concerns related to the data. This document is carefully aligned with the Horizon EU guidelines.

More specifically, in Section 3 we provide a summary of the data that are expected to be collected, processed, and exchanged throughout the DOSS project, discussed how these data will help towards the realization of the project's objectives, and presented a concrete template for their formal documentation. In Section 4 we describe how the open access data are planned to be made available to the public, along with how the FAIR principles will be satisfied. Section 5 provides information about the expected allocation of resources for ensuring the open accessibility of the project-related data and the assurance of compliance with the FAIR principles. In Section 6 we describe all the actions that will be taken in order to ensure the security of the project-related data, whereas in Section 7 we provide some remarks with respect to ethical aspects related to project data.

As DOSS is at a very early stage, and given the dynamic nature of the DMP as stated by the EC, the current deliverable is considered a living document and thus it will be updated during the project lifetime as needed, including more detailed information regarding the collected data, along with updates in our defined strategy, if this is considered necessary. In the periodic reports and in the next updated versions, as the DOSS project becomes more mature and actual research and technical work is carried out, we will provide more details on facets such as: (i) descriptions of the different datasets that will be collected, generated, and/or reused, including their reference, file format, standards, (ii) type and format of the data that will be exchanged among the various components of the DOSS project through their interfaces, (iii) structure and format of the DSP, which is the core means for communicating and exchanging security-related information within the proposed STC, and (iv) more details about license types and rules for the data producers to allow the widest reuse possible for the collected data.

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